

Cultures of AI in Practice

An Impact Report

basically you could just tell a machine to make an image and it might be better

I find that slightly concerning, you know, for lots of reasons

Patterns in Practice

Cultures of AI in Practice: An Impact Report

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An impact report for

Patterns in Practice: Cultures of data mining and
machine learning in science, education and the arts

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Cover and inner page: "An A.I. Sharing", Bristol Old Vic Adult Company & Tom Marshman, filmed by Eben Neale, 2024.
Report design by Lucy Sabin.

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Report summary

Patterns in Practice (2021-24) is a research project exploring how practitioners' beliefs, values, feelings and emotions shape how they engage with data mining and machine learning – techniques underlying many forms of 'narrow' artificial intelligence (AI) – across three industries and cultural contexts. Reflecting on multi-stakeholder engagement throughout the project, this report sets out to define, investigate, reflect and develop on the project's impact in its final stages. It offers a conceptualisation of impact as an iterative and empirical process involving knowledge exchange facilitated and enhanced by creative, collaborative, and dialogue-based methods.

First, we outline our qualitative research methodology, which comprised of interviews, focus groups and diaries with research participants working in the three target sectors of higher education, pharmaceutical drug discovery, and the arts. Drawing on feedback from the research participants, we explain how the methodology, by virtue of its conversational format, began to meet the impact aim of fostering critical dialogues among key stakeholders. Second, we outline how a more explicit approach to generating cross-sector dialogue was explicitly designed into the next phase of the project, drawing on and extending beyond four key themes emerging from early analysis of the qualitative studies (Medina-Perea et al., 2023a; Medina-Perea

et al., 2023b, Fraczkak et al., 2023). Two case studies are then presented showing the value of specific partnerships that supported artists with expertise in facilitating participatory, reflective, and performance-based critical dialogues and public conversations. In discussing the case studies, we find that partnering with a cultural organisation with the connections and capabilities to co-design, host and support artist collaborations is an effective means of sharing and exchanging practice-related knowledge beyond academia. This also developed our research in progress by contributing new insights, such as refining the emerging themes. A dialogue event series was designed to iteratively shape subsequent dialogues to share ideas and perspectives, alongside research evidence. Having a dedicated impact activity strand and associated resource can build partnerships and collaborations through co-design. This creates the conditions for the process of knowledge exchange to bridge gaps across industries and disciplinary specialisms within a broader cultural ecosystem.

The final part of the report offers both transferable and project-specific insights for evaluating and optimising impact in the future. We speculate about unexpected or unintended areas of impact, including the benefits that arise from incorporating diverse perspectives and creative methods into research at the intersection of human experiences and AI practices.

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Introduction

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Project overview

Patterns in Practice (PIP) is a research project that explores how practitioners' beliefs, values, feelings and emotions interact to shape how they engage with data mining and machine learning (ML) as techniques underlying forms of 'narrow' artificial intelligence (AI). **The overarching research aim was to promote awareness and understanding of these dynamics to help foster the development of critical and reflective data cultures.** To carry out the research, [the interdisciplinary research team](#) used a combination of interviews and focus groups and observations to investigate cultures of data practice in three sectors: pharmaceutical drug discovery, higher education (HE) learning analytics, and multidisciplinary arts.

An overarching aim of the impact activity strand was to engage differently situated practitioners through sharing our work at relevant festivals, conferences, publications, and through engaging practitioners in critically reflective dialogue. Throughout the research, in collaboration with key partners, we have curated, co-designed and facilitated in person and online events and dialogues to engage practitioners, relevant stakeholders, and wider publics. PIP was led by an interdisciplinary team with expertise in social science, digital culture, and impact at the University of Sheffield, and the Digital Cultures Research Centre (DCRC) at the University of the West of England (UWE) along with the following research partners and collaborators.

Illustration by Julie Bakay for PIP.

Research partners and collaborators

Pharmaceutical industry

GlaxoSmithKline Plc (GSK)

Higher education

Two UK universities

Jisc and its learning analytics network

Multidisciplinary arts

Arts practitioners (Commissioners, curators and artists)

Poet, Otis Mensah and Enon Films

Watershed's Pervasive Media Studio

Artist in Residence, Tom Marshman

Watershed's Pervasive Media Studio

Craig Scott

StrangeBrew, Bristol

Local arts audiences (Bristol and Sheffield)

Online arts audiences

AI dialogue partners

Diverse AI

Digital Cultures Research Centre (DCRC), UWE

AI Fringe

The Alan Turing Institute and DCRC

Artist Tom Marshman and Bristol Old Vic

Panellists and attendees of the cross-sector dialogues attendees

Practitioners spanning computing, engineering, finance

Sector- relevant practitioner conferences

ARLIS (Art Libraries)

EVA, International Electronic Visualisation and The Arts conference

Bristol & Bath Creative Summit

What benefits does AI bring to your community or culture?

Visual minutes by Julie Bakay for PIP.

Lunchtime Talk with Scott. Pervasive Media Studio, 2024.

Stakeholders and audiences

The primary stakeholders of this research are represented by the research partners and collaborators listed on page 3, including the research participants involved in the initial qualitative studies. Research participants were practitioners and decision makers involved in, or impacted by, data mining and ML in the three sectors of pharmaceutical drug discovery, learning analytics in HE, and the arts. Insights from the qualitative research are potentially transferable and may also be of relevance to AI users and other organisations across these three sectors, in other sectors, or anyone affected by AI in their working or learning environment.

In addition, researchers and research institutes that engage in social studies and initiatives in relation to AI technologies stand to benefit from our findings; several of these organisations are represented by our cross-sector partners such as Diverse AI. Those nonprofits and non-governmental bodies are concerned with AI practices and their impact on business and society as well as the general influence of technologies on working practices in each of the three target sectors. They could more concretely become users and beneficiaries of this research, given the potential to explore applications of the findings in relation to policy dialogue, responsible AI ethical frameworks, and social justice (see, for example, Bush et al., 2024).

In line with the aim of the impact strand, we recognise the importance of expanding discussions on AI practices beyond industry experts and academia to include secondary stakeholders spanning audiences and consumers affected by the three sectors in question. The effects of existing forms of AI and emerging developments on the general population are significant. AI-related topics, such as the usage of ChatGPT and Deepfakes, have resurfaced in public debate given the pervasive nature of AI and more recent technological advances, that have unfolding economic, cultural, and legal impacts. Many of our public engagement activities, such as a podcast series and short films, have been designed to use digital storytelling as a culturally relevant and accessible way to engage practitioners to attract interested publics via online and in person channels.

The Adult Company.
AI workshop with Tom Marshman.

and I think it opens up
lots of conversations about like

Initial qualitative research and impact in three sectors

- > Qualitative research with GSK (pharmaceutical)
- > Qualitative research with Higher Education (HE) partners
- > Qualitative research with arts practitioners

Initial qualitative research in three sectors

We first engaged with practitioners during the qualitative research phase. In total, 75 practitioners took part in focus groups and interviews. These participants were recruited from partner organisations: GSK, Jisc and its learning analytics network, and two UK universities. We also recruited individual arts practitioners who engage with forms of AI including artists, curators, and arts organisers. The objective of the interviews was to allow for in depth critical reflection on practitioners' beliefs, values, emotions and feelings towards AI practices in their workplace and industry. The interview sessions took place outside of participants' daily activities, while the focus groups brought together people in different roles to discuss key themes emerging from the interviews.

In a sense, the qualitative research methods reflected the overarching aim of Patterns in Practice to foster critical and reflective data cultures by facilitating encounters in which practitioners might express feelings, emotions, values, beliefs, and expert knowledge. **It is therefore important to consider the impact of qualitative research itself on the partner organisations and research participants who represent primary stakeholders.**

Conceivably, a general benefit of participating in the interviews and focus groups led by Patterns in Practice would be the opportunity for each participant to reflect on their own practice in a supportive and constructive setting.

There is some evidence to suggest that the qualitative research itself was

beneficial for participants because it provided dedicated spaces and times for them to voice concerns and – in the focus groups – to perhaps generate a sense of community or shared experience. Indeed, interview material suggests that practitioners care about and feel invested in the effects of data mining and machine learning on their ability to produce positive outcomes, to manage resources, and to build meaningful relationships at work (Medina Perea et al., 2023a; Medina-Perea et al., 2023b; Fraczak et al., 2023). The following three sections briefly outline and assess how we engaged with stakeholders in each sector.

Qualitative research with GSK (pharmaceutical)

For the research with GSK, a British multinational pharmaceutical and biotechnology company, we first shared the project internally via a talk that announced an open invite to participate aimed at people working on selected projects within the organisation. By signing up, participants demonstrated that the proposed research held value from their perspective. We did online interviews with 18 participants in different roles on three projects: computational chemists and biologists, medicinal and physical chemists, molecular biologists, scientific managers, and one computational scientist. We also conducted two focus groups at GSK Stevenage, each with five people in different roles. Findings from the

research were subsequently shared with GSK in a work in progress report (Medina-Perea et al., 2023a), which is available on the PIP website.

The report reveals how practitioners' beliefs, values, feelings and emotions shape how they engage with predictive machine learning techniques and outputs at different stages of the drug discovery pipeline. As such, the contents of the report raise concerns about working conditions, investment, and ultimately the effectiveness of AI tools. Feedback from some participants obtained in follow-up workshops suggests that the report reflected their understanding of challenges in the sector. To explore solutions to identified issues we have held 'Theory of Change' based workshops about pharma's 'bad data' problem with 25 GSK employees, including teams who were and were not involved in the original research. To track the ongoing impact of this line of inquiry, we plan to continue strategic

I find that slightly concerning, you know, for lots of reasons

The Adult Company. Filmed by Eben Neale.

communication with the partner organisation.

Qualitative research with Higher Education (HE) partners

For the research on machine learning and data mining in higher education, we carried out interviews (in person and online) and online focus groups with staff from Jisc, a UK nonprofit that supports digital resourcing in further and higher education. We also conducted interviews with staff from two UK universities that have implemented learning analytics (LA) systems, and people engaged in the Jisc LA network. We recruited a total of 33 participants from this sector.

The research had the intended benefit of helping Jisc and universities to “enhance [their] capacity to develop best practice guidelines for ethical practice, and HE institutions’ ability to make effective and ethical decisions about the adoption and use of learning analytics” (Medina-Perea et al., 2023b, p. 2). For example, during the qualitative research, practitioners raised concerns about the need to prioritise student-facing education and teacher-student interactions (pp.4-5).

The evidence we gathered also calls for a more targeted, user-centred approach to AI and careful investment in these technologies (p. 6). These insights do not necessarily lead to follow up actions, however. **Further evaluative research would be required to determine any subsequent behavioural benefits to stakeholders of participating in the research, the organisation’s response to the findings shared with them via the work in progress report, and to identify any further opportunities for sharing insights with stakeholders in the sector.**

Qualitative research with arts practitioners

Finally, we carried out a mix of online and face-to-face interviews and focus groups with 14 multidisciplinary arts practitioners to explore their perspectives on AI technologies in relation to their creative practices. Included in this group were arts practitioners based in the UK (artists, curators, and arts organisers) who use AI tools or engage with AI in their practice. The artists came from various disciplines, such as the visual arts, music, performance, installation, and combinations thereof. Unlike the other two groups of research participants, the art practitioners were freelance and/or affiliated with a range of different organisations.

As such, the focus groups with arts practitioners presented an opportunity for participants to learn from peers with whom they might not otherwise interact. Arts practitioners, particularly those who

are freelance, may not have immediate or institutional access to opportunities to share and build awareness through dialogue that would otherwise be possible through employment as a team member in a formal organisation.

Moreover, materials from the interviews and focus groups revealed "a range of ethical considerations which they [the practitioners] carefully navigate to make informed decisions about incorporating them into their work" (Fratczak et al., 2023, p. 5). In the absence of formal guidelines on AI in the creative industries, said considerations may positively influence practitioners' capacity to critically reflect on AI in their future projects, although **evaluative research with participants would be required to confirm this claim**. In addition, evidence from the "Cultures of AI practice in the arts" report may help to support arguments for "improved collaboration, funding, and understanding between the arts and computing fields" (p. 4).

Otis Mensah, ENON Films, and Patterns in Practice.

Creative approaches to knowledge exchange

- > Defining impact: an ecosystem of knowledge sharing
- > Case study: Craig Scott and the Pervasive Media Studio
- > Case study: Tom Marshman and the Adult Company, Bristol Old Vic

Defining impact: an ecosystem of knowledge sharing

Insights and analyses drawing on the qualitative research were initially communicated via three 'work in progress' reports that were published on the PIP website and circulated among our research partners and collaborators. The reports were useful in informing the subsequent development of further stakeholder and public engagement alongside knowledge exchange. Said activities reached wider audiences across industry sectors and the academic community, as well as members of the public. Insights from all three industry-related reports helped to inform and inspire any subsequent knowledge exchange, thus developing on the initial qualitative research while also increasing the impact of the project.

We engaged stakeholders and audiences both online and in person via conventional formats, such as conference presentations and panel discussions, as well as more innovative approaches including podcast episodes, artist collaborations, drama workshops and live performances. Most of the activities relate to our collaborations with multidisciplinary arts practitioners and arts organisations (Otis Mensah, Tom Marshman, Pervasive Media Studio, and Craig Scott) as well as Dialogue and Event partner organisations (Diverse AI, AI Fringe, Alan Turing Institute), which includes research groups undertaking AI public engagement activities. We also ran two 'theory of change' workshops with partner organisation GSK.

We have reached online audiences via multiple platforms: our Wordpress website and blog, the PIP podcast (available via Spotify, Apple Podcasts, Podbean and the project website), events streamed or recorded and uploaded to Youtube, and content shared on X (formerly Twitter). We only have 245 followers on X, so, the reach of any posts that we share from our @LifeofData account is minimal, and given recent changes to the platform its value for academic dissemination is now questionable. However, our social media presence remains an important dissemination channel because collaborators have significantly more followers and can post or reshare on our behalf (see the case studies below). Individual members of the team have also shared the project via their personal LinkedIn accounts.

Stakeholder engagement has promoted the dissemination of research insights and sparked discussions about AI in constructive, creative, and collaborative settings. In doing so, it has furthered the empirical aims of this project by generating spaces for critical reflection on values, beliefs, emotions and feelings relating to AI technologies. As we explore below, dialogue-based and creative approaches have come to play an integral role in the conceptual development of this research, with a direct impact on our forthcoming peer-reviewed publications, in which we intend to reference and draw insights from documentation of our podcast episodes

1 Averaging 272 hits per month over the last 6 months (source: Wordpress).

2 Produced by Samborne Bush. The first two episodes generated approx. 100 downloads each (source: Podbean).

and artist collaborations alongside data from the initial qualitative research. Given the empirical and dialogic role of stakeholder and public engagement throughout this project, it is important to define impact accordingly. That is, rather than viewing impact as a distinct intervention, we perceive the qualitative research, stakeholder and public engagement, and any resulting 'knowledge exchange' within a continuum of gathering evidence and building capacity. When beginning this impact assessment, we first gathered quantitative and qualitative data in relation to each impact activity, counting 29 completed or forthcoming 'events' or 'encounters' in total, including both academic and non-academic channels. However, it became apparent when viewing all the impact evidence together that the value of knowledge exchange cannot be fully appreciated when each activity is viewed in isolation. In other words, what we are looking at might be described or indeed visualised as an accumulative patchwork or ecosystem of knowledge exchange.

Each event might then be viewed as a contribution among others in a broader dialogue – maintaining our focus on dialogues from the initial qualitative research – that continues between events, during the planning phases, when researchers, stakeholders, and collaborators are building networks and co-creating new understandings. Many of our partners and stakeholders are already engaged with AI programmes and tools and in similar discussions so PIP has, through practices of curation and knowledge exchange, sought to elevate multiple voices and encourage timely dialogues in relation to situated AI practices. Artistic collaborations have played a key role in generating such dialogues in engaging and

multimedia ways. These collaborations have extended the possibilities of dialogue with wider publics, opening spaces for people to engage affectively and critically with the effects of AI practices and cultures that they encounter or observe in their personal experiences and communities.

Creative practices play an epistemological role in the project by re-interpreting and responding to insights gathered during the initial qualitative research, thus building on the research objective to foster critical dialogues. In other words, creative practices are an integral part of the research journey (Greenwood 2019). Incorporating creative processes, such as curation, within the overarching methodology has expanded our understanding of the subject matter as researchers and it has, in turn, enhanced the production of impactful scholarship (O'Neill & Wilson, 2015). As we mentioned in the previous section, we will cite, draw on, and analyse documentation of the creative collaborations in our forthcoming academic publications. Moreover, in the PIP podcast, the reflective dialogues with practitioners serve to tease out connections between research and practice in terms of storytelling (Bush 2024a, 2024b, 2024c; Parker Moon et al., 2023). Adopting a similar approach, we provide two case studies below to illustrate our conceptualisation of impact as an ecosystem of knowledge exchange.

In the case studies, we conduct an evaluation of two avenues of knowledge exchange that we pursued in collaboration with arts organisations and arts practitioners. The case studies are indicative of how impact was successfully enhanced throughout the project thanks to an evolving ecosystem of community building and knowledge sharing with

external collaborators and partners. These two examples highlight how our innovative and transdisciplinary approach to knowledge exchange in collaboration with non-academic partners and collaborators, including artistic practitioners, has made significant contributions to our empirical research and ongoing research outcomes. We show how dialogues unfolded throughout these collaborations, generating novel understandings of human-machine relations (one of the key themes emerging in our work in progress reports).

Case study: Craig Scott and Pervasive Media Studio

First, we teamed up with Watershed, a charity and social enterprise in Bristol focussing on creative technology, to co-design an artist research residency delivered by Watershed, that took place

between October 2023 and May 2024. Composer, improvising guitarist and sound artist, Craig Scott was selected for the residency hosted by Watershed's Pervasive Media Studio, an 'incubator' for creative technology innovation. Watershed runs artist residencies on a regular basis that feature curated public sharings and key opportunities for artists to share their progress with peers and publics. Led by Watershed, the PIP residency adopted this approach. Scott's practice explores creative possibilities at the intersection of human and machine-made music. Throughout the residency, Scott developed on this existing body of work in dialogue with both the Patterns in Practice team and Pervasive Media Studio's community of creative practitioners who experiment with technology.

During the residency, Scott innovated a process of making music that combined

Craig Scott at Strange Brew. Credit: Shampnat Photography.

analogue instrumentation with computer algorithms. In doing so, Scott responded to and developed on emerging insights from Patterns in Practice, specifically our initial qualitative research with participants in the pharmaceutical industry, higher education, and arts that identified themes around human-machine collaboration. Scott observed that “across all the industries [...] a lot of the AI processes [...] they felt were infringing on their personal creativity or the kind of spontaneity that is necessary to, I suppose, stumble across something that is wildly different and then would be considered a breakthrough later on down the line” (Bush 2024a).

As part of the art residency, Scott iteratively shared the work in progress at “Show and Test” events at the Pervasive Media Studio with five guitarists on one occasion and an audience of 29 members of the Watershed community on another. The conversational style and opportunity for audiences to ask questions and ‘play’ the instrument at these events increased the impact of the project through participatory involvement of audiences in the creative process, thus building relationships with practitioner networks and local audiences. Scott also reflected on the project during one of Watershed’s regular Friday “Lunchtime Talks”, reaching an in-person audience of 24 and an online audience of over 80.

The residency culminated in a final showcase event curated by Watershed in partnership with independent arts venue Strange Brew in Bristol on January 19, 2024. The event was open to the public with a live audience headcount of 77. General enthusiasm for the project was demonstrated by the long line of audience members who wished to meet Scott and see his instrument up close following the

performance. The event was also filmed and made public online via Scott’s YouTube channel and Instagram profiles. Watershed (@wshed) announced the residency via X, publishing a total of eight posts mentioning Craig Scott (@CSLobotomy) and/or the @LifeofData (PIP) account between October 2023 and January 2024, reaching an average of 1,000+ viewers per post.

Scott was interviewed several times as part of our collaboration, once for a short film shot on location during the residency (Watershed 2024) while on another occasion he was a main guest on the PIP podcast (Bush 2024a). In the video interview, Scott articulates the unique value of his collaboration with PIP: “it’s very interesting [for machine learning] to be approached from a felt, very human perspective, which can sometimes maybe be missing when people are talking about AI and machine learning”. Scott recounts how his own “felt” relationship with technology shifted during the residency as he began to experience a degree of “chaos” within that relationship, thus contributing a key insight to our ongoing research (Watershed 2024):

Up until recently, even within my own practice, I was thinking about digital control as kind of precision, exact repetition, but then with this it feels much more chaotic and it’s closer to the density of the surrounding of our digital world. So, it’s all very precise and everything, but there’s so much of it, and it’s happening at so many levels at once that it’s just this extremely, yeah, chaotic environment to be a part of.

A retrospective session with Scott, Watershed and PIP’s research and impact leads took place on May 29, 2024. Participants in the session reflected on how the residency had successfully linked with

both the research objectives and the community at Watershed. Everyone involved in coordinating the residency and showcase has agreed that the combination of arts and social sciences helped to generate novel research insights, such as how artistic practice embodies aspects of the research findings, thus opening the possibility to have a dialogue between creative practice and conceptual development. It was also stated that the significant investment in the artist residency meant that the collaboration period could last longer and offer greater support to the artist in developing their work further. Other benefits of this collaboration included the possibility to bring the research to wider audiences as

well as the new partnerships and networks formed beyond the University.

The partnership with Watershed has had a ripple effect on project impact beyond the artist residency and public performance with Scott's music furnishing the intro, outro, and interlude music for the podcast. Notably, Scott's guitar is to be showcased by the Victoria and Albert Museum during their Digital Design Weekend in September 2024 as part of the London Design Festival where the project is set to reach a wider public interested in digital technologies and design. In a feedback statement, Scott stated that the "residency has opened up new avenues of research within my own practice". He plans to continue developing and recording new forms of music production and artistic research.

Scott's guitar. Credit: Watershed via Youtube.

Craig Scott, filmed by Watershed.

Case study: Tom Marshman and Bristol Old Vic Adult Company

The second case study is based on our collaboration with Bristol-based dramatist and actor, Tom Marshman, whose work explores cultural narratives of otherness, with a focus on LGBTQ+ experiences. Marshman's use of archives and storytelling illuminates hidden queer histories, shedding light on untold stories. Marshman was in the process of designing and subsequently facilitating a 10-week workshop series with 25 actors from the Adult Company at Bristol Old Vic, a participatory theatre class that requires no prior experience. Marshman was aware of Patterns in Practice through Pervasive Media Studios and approached the PIP team to express their interest to find out more about insights from the research. In dialogue with PIP, Marshman facilitated a dramaturgical journey for the Adult Company that set out to explore "the need for unruly personal stories in the AI era", as per the title given to the workshop series. Marshman guided participants as they devised short dramatic pieces that reflected on human interactions with AI from their own unique perspectives of self-inquiry. The workshops culminated in a performance entitled "An A.I. Sharing" at Bristol Old Vic, with approximately 150 attendees in a sold-out show (April 26, 2024). The Adult Company reported that the sessions provided them with a space to explore their feelings about AI, with one actor stating, "I've learned [...] more about humanity [...] because what we've been working with is [...] very unhuman" (Marshman 2024b).

TM = Tom Marshman

P = Participant

TM The three words that I would use to describe this project are expanding, humane, and robotic.

P1 eclectic, inclusive, and uncertain

P2 intellectual, personal, calm

P3 exploratory, challenging, filled with potential

P4 informative, enjoyable, and thirdly caution!!

P5 explorative, innovative, personal! That is, that was the crux of the piece, I think.

The collaboration with Marshman contributed a uniquely personal, biographical, and polyvocal dimension to the Patterns in Practice project. Another performer shared that, "It was very interesting to witness everybody's reactions to the AI, and everybody's different perspectives from their different backgrounds, across different ages" (Marshman 2024a). By adopting a personal approach, Marshman developed on the Patterns in Practice theme of "Human v machine – creativity and complexity", which corresponds to a common experience among research participants working with forms of AI in the pharmaceutical industry (Medina-Perea 2023, 5-6). One research participant reported, "What I would really want from AI/ML is to give me an idea I'd never think of" (6), but instead they have experienced a "deficit of surprise" (Bates et al., 2023) – one of the emerging themes from PIP that Marshman adopted during our collaboration:

We looked at some of the ideas around how there's a kind of human-machine collaboration going on and what that

would look like going forward within the work that we were creating together. And we talked about that deficit of surprise. Some [members] of the group were women, older women perhaps, that have been dealing with misogyny for all of their lives. So, there was this kind of like, well, it's not really that surprising that AI is going to come up with something that feels like intrinsically misogynistic or is less centred around a woman's experience.

“An A.I. Sharing” humorously demonstrated a deficit of surprise in human-machine collaboration, which ties in with a perceived lack of creativity in predictive modelling and its current limitations in responding to the complexity and diversity of human experiences. For example, the production featured a dialogue with an AI chatbot whereby the actor would ask philosophical questions and receive predictable,

mundane, or biased answers (see below). The latter strikes an interesting contrast with the chaos that Scott experienced while composing music in collaboration with AI; whereas Scott was directly involved in programming his modified instrument, users of AI do not have the agency to influence algorithms directly to produce desirable results. In Marshman’s words, the collaboration opened up “conversations about [...] who are the decision makers in this process?” (Marshman 2024a).

Actor performing AI Ultimately, the best way for Marian to be happy is...

Marian (with eager anticipation): ...yes?!

Actor.. AI ...is to discover what works for them and practise it regularly

Marian (Gestures to the crowd and sighs)

Marshman & Justin Knapp,
filmed by Eben Neale.

An A.I. Sharing, Bristol Old Vic, 2024.

Throughout our collaboration with Marshman, we reinforced connections across other aspects of the project. In preparation for the workshop series, we invited the Adult Company to attend Scott's final showcase at Strange Brew, Bristol, where he had the opportunity to engage with Scott's work and thinking on creative human-machine collaboration. Additionally, Marshman was inspired by our podcast interview with 'I Am Echoborg' (Bush 2024b), which influenced the inclusion of an Echoborg-like disembodied character in "An A.I. Sharing". Looking to the future, Marshman plans to continue his work at the intersection of archives and AI technology, maintaining his focus on untold stories and what he calls "unruly" lives (quoted from Bush 2024c):

I think that we are only at the beginning of this journey with AI in terms of being a creative practitioner and responding to that...and when AI was developed, I'm

pretty sure that people that have unruly lives or queer lives or people that are affected with disabilities or maybe even people of colour, their stories are less present within that so I feel like as an artist my responsibility is kind of to say what about us, you know?

Filmed by Eben Neale.

Bristol Old Vic Adult Company. Filmed by Eben Neale.

Final reflections

- > Recommendations for measuring impact
- > Opportunities for ongoing knowledge exchange
- > Insights and ideas for impactful research in the future

We have faced several challenges when generating and evaluating impact across PIP: the project investigates subjective experiences rather than concrete variables; it is future-oriented, so impacts might not show up in the short-term; and there are multiple groups of stakeholders, practitioners, and audiences to consider from very different sectors or communities. In addition, individual members of the team engaged with specific stakeholders and collaborators, so the writing of this report has required retrospective dialogues with one another to collate our collective knowledge. In doing so, we have arrived at a better understanding of the shape and force of impact in this research. Rather than viewing impact as a series of isolated events, we have generated an understanding of impact as an ecosystem of knowledge sharing and building capacity through the accumulative benefits of curated, critical, creative, and ongoing forms of dialogue.

The arts is perhaps unique in being closer to its audiences, and having the necessary public infrastructure (both online and face to face) compared to other sector case studies. As such knowledge sharing dialogues would require new partners and resources to distribute dialogues across all of the stakeholder groups. This was beyond the scope of the research project. Hence the necessity for a critical evaluation of impact that identifies further opportunities for knowledge exchange. The case studies and the overall distribution of impact evidence show that there are several successful examples of multi-phase stakeholder engagement activities that adopted arts-based approaches. These activities responded in various ways to the qualitative research across all sectors (i.e., not just the arts), with a fair amount of

dissemination evidence (audience numbers, documented feedback, artist interviews, documented events, retrospective sessions, social media stats, and so on). In addition, there are numerous examples of stakeholder engagement with AI awareness organisations that successfully situate the project in relation to emergent research frameworks and ethical concerns, although we have less qualitative evidence as to the ongoing benefits or changes resulting from these activities.

While the qualitative research across all three industries informed subsequent stakeholder engagement activities with arts/AI organisations and interested publics. As noted earlier, there has been comparatively less follow-up engagement activities with pharmaceutical and higher education stakeholders in the period following the initial qualitative research. However each case study is featured in a podcast, which offers the opportunity to generate further impact, shared through the right channels. Several activities, analyses, and practitioner publications are also being developed throughout the next period to address this imbalance and reach stakeholders through industry-specific channels. Some progress has already been made regarding the pharmaceutical industry. For instance, the team recently facilitated 'Theory of change' workshops with participants from GSK, gathering evaluation data from 20 practitioners, which we are currently analysing. PI Jo Bates also joined the global steering committee of Hitchhikers AI, a network investigating AI adoption in biopharma.

The comparatively lower amount of impact evidence regarding stakeholder engagement in pharmaceuticals and HE learning analytics suggests a need to

continue to prioritise impact and engagement with said groups. This objective is reflected by the recommendations below. The next section identifies how insights from this evaluative impact report might inform the next steps of Patterns in Practice as the project enters its final stages. It covers lessons for evaluating impact, recommendations for stakeholder engagement that can be implemented in the short term, and more speculative suggestions for related research that might take place in the future based on the success stories of this project.

Otis Mensah, ENON Films, and PIP.

Recommendations for measuring impact

Based on this report, there are several lessons we might take forward in the next period when it comes to measuring and evaluating impact.

- **Evaluative research is needed to find out the immediate benefits of participating in the research.** To reach a better understanding of the applicability, usefulness and transferability of the research for participants and colleagues at GSK and Jisc, HE organisations and in the arts sector, we can survey members of our research team involved in the empirical work and/or follow up with contacts in the organisation to see if any changes or benefits resulted from participation in the interviews and focus groups.
- **Evaluative research is needed to obtain feedback from industry practitioners on the work in progress reports (and this could take place in forthcoming events).** For example, as in recent workshops with practitioners in the pharmaceutical industry, we could distribute print versions of the reports and solicit feedback at workshops aimed at higher education. The objective would be to gauge how transferable insights from the reports are, and how these insights might contribute to future activity from the PiP team aimed at fostering changes or benefits. We could also contact specific individuals and project partners for statements. For example, through continued dialogues with Diverse AI, we have ascertained that our collaboration has helped shape their plans for future projects to make more accessible language models (Bush et al., 2024).
- **A Team survey would capture additional insights that may be unexpected or overlooked.** Each team member may specialise in a particular group / sector, so we would benefit from a collective reflection on impact. A team survey has been circulated with three parts relating to impact objectives, dissemination, and professional development within the team. The survey is designed to gather multiple perspectives into one place and cover any unexpected impact evidence, ideas for stakeholder engagement, and reflections on how the project has impacted us as researchers and, where applicable, in our capacity as educators.
- **We need to build in ways of measuring impact as we go on.** The way we do this will depend on the format of the engagement. For example, at a workshop, we might keep track of audience numbers and make a note of audience engagement (event ethnography). Event design could also include interactive elements that allow us to record and capture responses such as a live illustration, feedback forms or facilitated discussions in which to share feedback collectively. The retrospective session with Watershed is a good example of follow through.

Opportunities for ongoing knowledge exchange

Based on this report, there are several lessons for ongoing stakeholder and public engagement that could be implemented in the short-term.

- **To address the need for more engagement with the pharmaceutical industry and higher education, we plan to share the research in practitioner publications.** The articles we write will build on the empirical research by addressing topics that professional audiences care about. In doing so, we might expand our conceptualisation of stakeholders in industry to encompass decision-makers as well as practitioners (noting that there is often overlap), thus increasing the potential for impact at multiple levels.
- **Focussing on promoting our recently published and forthcoming podcast episodes may increase impact in relation to pharmaceuticals and education.** The final two episodes cover AI in higher education and AI in pharmaceutical drug discovery, both with practitioner interviews and contemplation of emerging and future developments in AI practices. As part of podcast dissemination, we can continue to support interview guests to distribute the episodes among their professional networks, for example via their X and/or LinkedIn accounts as well as newsletters and bulletins that circulate among their colleagues and peers.
- **We could share, reshare, cross-post, and engage on social media in a strategic way** to a) extend the impact of existing and underused multimedia content and, b) boost audiences and generate discussion in response to ongoing dissemination activities and practitioner publications. Previously, we have used X more regularly in our attempts to maximise the impact and reach of events and outputs. Analytics show that while our following is limited to 338 users (as of September 2, 2024), when posts are reshared by our more influential collaborators, views drastically increase, suggesting an alternative focus when measuring impact. The proposed shift is to ultimately drive reshares by mentioning our collaborators and producing content that they would also wish to promote. To this end, we recommend creating more visual content (infographics, videos, images), which typically drives more engagement than just text across the board.
- **A similar approach to relationship-building via social media could be applied to LinkedIn.** There is the possibility of reaching out to targeted networks of professionals in pharmaceuticals and learning analytics especially by joining LinkedIn Groups or writing LinkedIn blog posts that summarise the work in progress. For example, members of the PIP Team recently collaborated with partners at

Diverse AI in a joint launch of the co-authored report (Bush et al. 2024) across X and LinkedIn. These online channels are not to be seen as separate from the practitioner publications or forthcoming workshops, but as part of a continuum of impact.

- **When sharing content on social media or via time-sensitive platforms like newsletters, we will continue to plan ahead using a scheduling calendar.** For example, an important milestone will be the exhibition of Scott's work at the V&A Digital Design Weekend in September 2024. In collaboration with Scott and Pervasive Media Studio, we will promote the event in advance via online channels using existing multimedia content. During the Weekend, we could also document the installation, observe visitor responses, and, in the aftermath, partake in reflective discussions.

Shamphat Photography.

Otis Mensah filmed by ENON Films in collaboration with PIP.

Insights and ideas for impactful research in the future

Based on this report, there are several insights and ideas that could be explored in the future as an extension of the research or in follow-up projects.

- **The impact of the research might be framed in terms of diversity, accessibility, and inclusion in dialogues on AI technologies.** Diversity was not an explicit focus of the original research proposal for PIP, although the research team found ways to promote diversity in practice for example in the art commissions. Overall, the diversity of perspectives on AI technologies generated by this research, both in terms of diversity within the team and stakeholders who we engaged through creative forms of knowledge exchange, may be regarded as a wider benefit of PIP. Studies have indicated that gender diverse teams are more likely to tackle socially engaged aspects of AI research (Stathoulopoulos and Mateos-Garcia, 2019). To give an example, our ‘Developing Critical AI Cultures’ report in collaboration with Diverse AI and practitioners who are underrepresented in the tech industry has underscored the importance of making large language models more accessible and inclusive for sign language users (Bush et al., 2024). Moreover, participants in “An A.I. Sharing” drew attention to queer and feminist experiences of AI, as discussed in our second case study.
- **Further dialogues with key stakeholders in industry might take the form of participatory workshops that focus on changes and benefits.** We have trialled such an approach and we are still analysing qualitative data gathered during the ‘Theory of Change’ workshops at GSK on July 3, 2024. Yet we have an early indication that the workshop format was successful in disseminating our research with key stakeholders and evaluating its impact while contributing empirical insights to the ongoing research. As such, we plan to adopt a similar format with practitioner groups in higher education.
- **The impact of the research could be enhanced by learning from the success of our art-research collaborations and employing similar methods in future.** Artistic methods, including curation, have been a means of sharing the research to public audiences while also contributing empirical insights. Our collaborations with Watershed demonstrated the value of involving artists and communities in ongoing discussions that take place over a longer duration whereby creative processes open up spaces for critical and reflective dialogue. Learning from these success stories, similar lines of inquiry could be explored in more depth as empirical, creative research.

- **Finally, we might contribute to ongoing conversations about ethics, best practices, and policy in adjacent fields in terms of, say, medical ethics or pedagogy as practice.** Our research outputs are capacity-building resources for peers who are developing general frameworks and guidelines for practitioners. The dialogues continue beyond Patterns in Practice. We plan to continue participating in conversations that speak to ethics, best practices, and policy. Indeed, we had planned to address our findings to the Department of Education, although this activity has been postponed due to the 2024 General Election. By participating in dialogues that critically reflect on AI practices in societal contexts, we stand to situate our research within broader regimes of practice which by extension have a bearing on ethics frameworks, guidelines for best practices, and the shape-shifting policy landscapes at the forefront of emerging technologies and human-computer interactions.

and digitally controlled
from the computer.

Both images: Craig Scott filmed by Watershed.

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